

IMPACT OF "SHELTER" OBJECT ON GROUNDWATER

Igor P. Onyshchenko¹, Vyacheslav M. Shestopalov¹, Mykola I. Panasyuk², Volodymyr M. Shcherbin²
and Mikhail G. Buzinny³

¹Radioecological Center, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. 55-b, Gonchar St., Kyiv, Ukraine

²Interdisciplinary Scientific and Technical Center "Shelter", National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.
36 Kirov St., Chernobyl, Ukraine

³Research Center for Radiation Medicine, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine St., Kyiv, Ukraine

Abstract: *The paper describes the chemical and radiochemical composition of groundwater, soil contamination with radionuclides and geological-hydrogeological structure in the area of Shelter Object (SO) and Chernobyl NPP location. The possible sources of groundwater contamination with radionuclides and other type of contaminants are considered. The conclusion was made about two existing principle sources of groundwater technogenous contamination in the area of SO location. They are: (1) superficial soil layer which was highly contaminated during the accident at Chernobyl NPP and then buried under thick layer of technogenous deposits (in the course of accident consequences liquidation); (2) probable income of SO internal waters to geological environment.*

INTRODUCTION

The accident at the Chernobyl NPP, happened in 1986, could be undoubtedly ascribed to one of the greatest technogenous catastrophes of the modern civilization. Into the epicenter of the accident there were involved large territories of Ukraine and Byelorussia, which are now referred to as the Chernobyl exclusion zone. In its scale and diversity of the negative consequences the Chernobyl accident turned to be the national tragedy for the people of Ukraine, Byelorussia and Russia. Its influence can be traced to this or that degree in many countries of Europe, Asia and all over the world.

The Chernobyl exclusion zone within the Ukraine borders covers the area of 2044.4 km². Besides, after peoples evacuation from the large territories the excluded areas automatically extended approximately by 1800 km². As a whole, this area exceeds the territory of such an European state as Luxemburg by 1.5 times (Atlas of Chernobyl exclusion zone edited by Shestopalov 1996).

As a result of explosion the active zone and the upper part of reactor was completely destroyed. Barriers and safety systems protecting environment from radionuclides produced by irradiated fuel, were also ruined. Therefore, immediately after the accident the most urgent problem was to erect the structure available to protect environment from further spreading of radionuclides out of destroyed NPP 4th unit as well as working personnel from exposure to radiation. It took only six months to build the construction which had no analogues in world practice. This construction was called the "Shelter" object (SO).

Geological environment and particularly groundwater in SO area acquired the unique radiochemical composition. The main factors of this composition formation were high radioactive pollution of surrounding territory, as well as ingress of various chemical reagents used during fire extinguishing, taking preventing measures against chain reaction appearance, deactivation, etc. Finally we can not exclude the probability of migration of highly active internal SO waters to geological environment. The objective of given paper is to study the dynamics of radiochemical and hydrochemical composition of groundwater in the area of SO location.

1. GEOLOGICAL-HYDROGEOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF THE STUDY AREA

The SO site and adjacent area is located on the right-bank of the first above flood-plain terrace of the Prypiat river (the largest tributary of the Dnieper) at a distance of 0.8 km from the terrace cusp. Prior to the accident at Chernobyl NPP the elevations of land surface ranged from 113.5 to 116.0 m. At present the elevation of SO site above flood plain of Prypiat river is about 5-9 m. Slop gradient (following river direction) does not exceed 0.002.

In geological composition of the area the following deposits take part (from top to bottom):

- Quaternary alluvial deposits containing unconfined aquifer;
- low-permeable layer of Kyiv suite marls of Eocene;
- water-bearing complex in Buchak and Kanev suites of Eocene.

The geological deposits underlying those listed above are free from surface contamination influence and hence they are not considered in the given paper.

In the course of hydrogeological studies the thickness of Quaternary aquifer was determined to be 25-28 m, depth of unsaturated zone 5-10 m. Groundwater is in contact with foundation of SO bottom premises. Unsaturated zone is composed of both technogenous soils (formed during the Chernobyl NPP construction and accident consequences liquidation) and Quaternary deposits.

The Quaternary deposits within unsaturated zone are represented by fine- and medium-grained sands with sandy loam and loam inter-beds. The conductivity of water-bearing rocks is 15-20 m/day - for medium-grained sands, 2-4 m/day for fine-grained sands, 1-2 m/day for powdered sands, 0.1 m/day - for loam, 0.5 m/day - for sandy loam.

The magnitude of groundwater table fluctuations in 1996-1997 equaled 0.4-0.6 m. The groundwater flow gradient was 0.001 m/m. In summer period groundwater temperature varied from 10.4 °C to 14.2 °C.

Quaternary aquifer recharges from atmospheric precipitation, technological leakage (losses from transportation links, cooling pond and supply channels). It discharges directly to the Prypiat river or aged runs in the flood-plain.

Low-permeable layer of Kyiv suite of the Eocene is about 10 m in thickness. It is composed of marly clays and marls. Conductivity of deposits is estimated ranging from 2,5E-4 to 1,8E-2 m/day. Given layer is of regional occurrence and separates upper unconfined Quaternary aquifer from underlying confined ones. Water-bearing rocks of Buchak and Kanev suites of the Eocene are 40 m in thickness. They are represented by sands including sandstone, siltstone and clay inter-beds. They contain confined aquifer. The piezometric surface closely approximates the water table of unconfined Quaternary aquifer. Eocene aquifer is drained in the valleys of Dnieper and Prypiat river.

2. POSSIBLE SOURCES OF GROUNDWATER RADIONUCLIDE CONTAMINATION

The most dangerous factors influencing the geological environment are: possible migration of contaminated water outside the SO and highly radiocontaminated territory of SO site.

2.1. Inter waters of SO

In the course of studies the principle ways of water income to SO premises were determined. They are: atmospheric precipitation, moisture condensation and technological solutions. Inside the SO water moves along the principal water pathways. Depending on weather conditions its discharge can vary in large ranges (up to 800 m³/year) (Borovoy et al., 1996).

After interaction with concrete water takes on alkaline carbonate composition and gains the capacity to dissolve cesium and uranium compounds. Water flow washes out the fuel-containing mass and remove the fuel particles and soluble radionuclides. Eventually water is accumulated in the bottom SO premises. In some cases the water level inside SO is much higher than groundwater table in the adjacent to SO area that can lead to water migration outside the SO, its income to groundwater and then to the rivers.

Internal waters are of chloride-hydrocarbonate, potassium-sodium macro-composition, with alkaline reaction (pH 7,6-10,5) and mineralization from 1,6 to 12 g/l, (p.120 and p.30 tab 1). They are characterized by increased phosphate concentration. The internal SO waters can be divided symbolically into two groups. In the first group hydrocarbonate and carbonate ions are dominated (60-74 % mg-equivalent) in anion composition whereas in cation composition– potassium and sodium are prevalent. Waters are characterized by alkaline reaction (pH >9) and high mineralization (up to 12g/l).

Chemical composition of the second group is characterized by low mineralization (1-2 g/l), high relative concentration of chloride ions (40-75 % mg-equivalent), rather low concentration of hydrocarbonate (17-48 % mg-equivalent) and carbonate ions (< 1 %). In cation composition sodium and potassium dominate. Oxidation-reduction (redox) potential varies from –83 mV to –112 mV corresponding to reduction conditions.

Microcomponent concentration in internal SO waters are rather different. Concentration of As, Pb, Se, Rb, W, Si are raised as compared to their clarkes. Distinct dependencies between concentrations of micro- and macro-elements in waters were not revealed.

Concentration of ⁹⁰Sr in internal waters of SO bottom premises amounts to high levels. At present the maximal volume of internal SO waters (about 200 m³) is located in so-called compartment 001/3 where in August 1998 concentration of ⁹⁰Sr in water ran to 9 000,000 Bq/l, concentration of ¹³⁷Cs being 9 400,000 Bq/l. In the single samples concentration of ¹³⁷Cs in water ranges up to 61 000,000 Bq/l (Krinityn et al., 1998).

Since the assumption can be made of microcracks occurrence in SO concrete foundation, resulted from the explosion at power unit, though there exists a possibility of incoming the highly active internal SO waters to geological environment. In this connection occurrence of carbonate-ions in the inter-block waters and their alkaline reaction can serve as a positive factor. In such conditions strontium (including radioactive one) is precipitated from solution forming poorly soluble strontium carbonate. Sorption characteristics of geological environment and small rate of groundwater flow also prevent from radionuclide migration out of SO. However, we must always take into account theoretical possibility of income of highly active internal waters to geological environment.

2.2. Soils composition

The other source of groundwater contamination is the highly contaminated area around the SO containing at the land surface 0.5 % of nuclear fuel and different active zone elements ejected from reactor. Deactivation works performed in 1986-1987 considerably improved the radiation situation around the destroyed 4th unit of Chernobyl NPP. Hence, by the moment of completion of the SO construction the radiation level at the site equaled 0.3-1.2 R/hour (compared to 40-1000 R/hour as of 1 August, 1986). However, the large amount of fuel still remained on the operating site covered by the artificial bank composed of gravel-sand mixture, concrete and asphalt coating. It was built as a special radiation-resistant layer to reduce the radiation level. The remained fuel mass is a real danger for environment because that artificial bank can't provide for safe isolation from physical-chemical influence of natural and technogenous factors.

The soils within SO site were studied with radiochemical and radiometric methods by analyzing core samples and wells gamma-logging. Uranium, plutonium and products of nuclear fuel fission were identified by laboratory analysis of core samples.

The highest concentration of uranium ($5.11E-2\%$) was detected in the north-eastern part of SO site at the depth of 2.6-2.9 m pre-accidental land surface. In the deeper soil samples the uranium concentration does not exceed $8E-4\%$. Within the zone of natural soils it equals $nE-5\%$, where "n" ranges from 1 to 10.

In sampled soils plutonium concentration correlates with that of uranium, its maximal value is close to that of uranium and equals $1.6E+4$ Bq/g. In the deeper soil samples the plutonium concentration does not exceed 1-13.4Bq/g, within natural soils zone it is 0.01Bq/g and less.

At present short-living fission products (^{144}Ce , ^{106}Ru , ^{125}Sb , ^{154}Eu , ^{60}Co) are identified only in the sampled soils with high uranium concentration by gamma-spectrum at long exposition of measuring.

^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr was found in all geological zones in different concentrations. Maximal concentration of ^{137}Cs was observed in well 4g ($5.2E+5$ Bq/g) and 9-1A ($8.7E+4$ Bq/g) at the depth of pre-accidental land surface. Minimal ^{137}Cs concentrations (0.3-0.6 Bq/g) were observed in the natural soils zone.

^{90}Sr concentration in post-accidental technogenous deposits varies from 0.2 to $4.8E+5$ Bq/g. Maximal concentrations are associated with (pre-accidental land surface). In the upper part of the Quaternary aquifer ^{90}Sr concentrations are 0.05-0.2 Bq/g.

Therefore, in vertical cross-section of study area the most radiocontaminated are the soils near pre-accidental land surface, the less contaminated are post-accidental technogenous deposits. Water migration of radionuclides or their mechanical removal caused contamination of pre-accidental soils (both technogenous and natural).

3. GROUNDWATER COMPOSITION

3.1. Chemical composition of groundwater

Taking into account the importance of controlling the cases of penetration of highly active internal waters to groundwater hydrosphere, the chemical composition of superficial aquifer within the SO site was studied. The objective of this study was identification of those elements and compounds which could serve as an evidence of ingress of the internal SO waters to groundwater. As a basis it was taken the list of chemical substances used during fire extinguishing, lowering the reactor criticality, deactivation, dust-depressing and those injected into the damaged power unit. This list involved non-organic and organic acids H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , HCl , H_3PO_4 , $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{OH})[\text{P}(\text{O})(\text{OH})_2]_2$, alkali (KOH and NaOH), silicates, alcohol, organic reagents ($\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$, $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{As}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_{14}\text{S}_2$, $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{OSO}_3\text{Na}$, $[-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OCOCH}_3)-]_m$), boron compounds, lead, petroleum refining products, etc.

Hydro-geochemical mapping of water composition for Quaternary aquifer in the borders of SO site was performed according to the data from existing observation hydrogeological wells. Based on given mapping the hydrochemical characteristic of groundwater was made, the maps were built of specific element concentration in groundwater, time-variation of concentrations was followed.

Groundwater chemical composition within the Chernobyl NPP operating site (including SO) is of mozaic character which is peculiar to the territories subjected to intensive technogenous influence. Within relatively small area groundwater of different anion and cation composition occurs, tab 1.

Tab.1 Chemical composition of groundwater from some wells on the "Shelter's" operating site and. inter waters of SO (p.120, p.30)

Parameters	well 13-1A	well 5-1A	well 10-1A	well 4-G	well 9-1A	well 1-G	p.102	p.30
Sampling date	3.12.98	1.12.98	1.12.98	3.12.98	9.12.98	9.12.98	25.06.97	25.06.97
pH	6.1	6.0	5.6	6.8	6.1	6.7	9.3	6.5
Eh, mV	+260	+275	+295	+230	+250	+190	-95	-80
Na^+ , mg/l	32.6	15.0	79.4	17.1	30.0	47.5	Na+K= 2389.9	Na+K= 380.3
K^+ , mg/l	1.5	2.0	5.6	16.4	3.8	16.3		
Ca^{2+} , mg/l	20.0	40.1	72.1	12.0	44.1	2.0	3.6	23.0
Mg^{2+} , mg/l	2.4	9.7	14.6	4.8	8.5	0.7	1.8	6.7
NH_4^+ , mg/l	0.5	0.2	2.0	1.1	0.1	0.4	6.5	0.1
$\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{3+}$, mg/l	18.4	6.1	94.9	3.2	21.7	5.0	0.8	2.5
Cl^- , mg/l	13.8	11.9	21.4	4.8	14.2	4.2	28.4	43.3
SO_4^{2-} , mg/l	44.0	95.8	292.9	24.6	109.0	28.8	722.2	234.1
NO_3^- , mg/l	0.5	3.6	62.7	6.5	8.4	15.2	6.0	34.6
NO_2^- , mg/l	-	0.1	0.3	-	-	-	32.0	-
CO_3^{2-} , mg/l	-	-	-	-	-	-	990.2	-
HCO_3^- , mg/l	57.9	54.9	57.9	85.4	94.6	97.6	3356.0	707.8
F^- , mg/l	0.5	0.8	0.3	1.2	-	1.5	-	-
PO_4^{3-} , mg/l	-	-	-	5.0	-	1.0	0.1	2.2
Mineralization, mg/l	192.1	240.2	704.1	182.1	334.4	220.2	7537.5	1434.6

The natural type (by chemical composition) of groundwater within above flood-plain terraces of the north part of Ukraine is hydrocarbonate calcium and magnesium-calcium water with mineralization about 200 mg/l.

Construction of Chernobyl NPP, its exploitation and especially liquidation of the nuclear accident consequences had a great impact on groundwater chemical composition formation comparable with nature processes. The technogenous processes often were the determinative factor of groundwater composition formation.

As technogenous influence is increased, the chemical composition of groundwater changes from hydrocarbonate-calcium and magnesium-calcium to sulphate-hydrocarbonate, hydrocarbonate-sulphate** and finally chloride-sulphate and nitrate-sulphate type (by dominating anions) with calcium-sodium and potassium-sodium cation composition.

Small concentration of sulphates in water can be explained by natural processes of its chemical composition formation, whereas their preference, especially against the chlorides and nitrates appearance in anion composition as well as sodium and potassium cations uniquely indicates the penetration of technogenous contaminants into groundwater.

After studying from this position of groundwater types distribution over the Chernobyl NPP site, it was concluded that the general direction of technogenous contamination expansion is from south-western to north and north-western part of the Chernobyl NPP operating site. Groundwater sampled from the wells located to the south-west from SO is of hydrocarbonate-calcium composition, whereas under the 3^d and 4th power units and then in the north direction the composition of sampled groundwater is changed to hydrocarbonate-sulphate, sulphate-hydrocarbonate anion type with prevailing sodium cation (Onyshchenko et al., 1998).

It was determined the increased concentration in groundwater of such microelements as Pb (up to 390 µg/l), Br (up to 540 µg/l), Rb (up to 64 µg/l). The greatest concentrations of lead were determined in wells close to SO (in the direction of groundwater flow).

Occurrence in the groundwater of elements and compounds (sodium, potassium, sulphates, nitrates, iron, fluorine, phosphates, organic agents, lead) which had been injected into damaged reactor, and their raised concentration in the direction of groundwater flow can indicate in our view the possible income of internal waters into subsurface hydrosphere.

3.2. Radiochemical composition of groundwater

Radiochemical composition of groundwater is characterized by radionuclides of ⁹⁰Sr, ¹³⁷Cs, ²³⁸Pu, ²³⁹⁺²⁴⁰Pu, ²⁴¹Am, ³H (T). The concentration of given radionuclides in groundwater within the study area varies in the following range:

⁹⁰Sr- from 2 Bq/l up to 720 Bq/l (excluding problematic well 3-G in which all-time high concentration of radiostrontium (up to 3820 Bq/l) are fixed that probably may be caused by penetration of storm-drainage water;

¹³⁷Cs – from 6 Bq/l up to 1734 Bq/l;

²³⁸Pu - from 0,0096 Bq/l up to 3 Bq/l;

²³⁹⁺²⁴⁰Pu - from under 0,0037 Bq/l up to 5,6 Bq/l;

²⁴¹Am - from under <0,0015 Bq/l up to 8,5 Bq/l

There was not revealed any distinct regularity of radionuclides spacial distribution in groundwater, which could indicate their coming from SO. As already noted, this can be associated with special characteristics of physical-chemical situation inside SO, preventing migration of radionuclides as well as sorption properties of geological environment and low rate of groundwater flow.

On the other hand, during the period of April-July 1997 the increase of strontium concentration in groundwater was fixed in the wells within Chernobyl NPP operating site. This period was also characterized by large atmospheric precipitation (over one-third of annual rate), and hence intensive groundwater infiltration recharge. Correlation between these two factors testifies that radionuclides penetrate into groundwater with infiltration flow from aeration zone. It follows that highly contaminated soils is the source of groundwater radionuclide contamination.

Tritium being heavy hydrogen isotope is also beta-emitter with relatively low radiation energy (0.018 MeV). Half-life period of tritium is 12.26 years. In water tritium occurs in the form of HTO molecules, rarely in the form of T₂O and DTO molecules. Tritium is accumulated in the nuclear reactor in the heat-generating elements, in regulating bars, in graphite moderator and also in heat transfer.

For a number of reasons tritium was taken as an indicator of internal SO waters arrival to geological environment: These reasons are as follows:

- internal SO waters contain considerable amount of tritium;
- tritium being the chemical analogue of hydrogen in geological media possess migration properties similar to those of simple water.

In the course of studies sampling of surface, internal and groundwater was performed. Inside SO sampling was carried out in the bottom premises adjacent to geological media. The activity of tritium was studied in the laboratory of Ukrainian Research Center for Radiation Medicine by fluid scintillation beta-spectrometer QUANTULUS 1220 TM.

Tritium is absent in lava-like fuel-containing mass because it was formed at a temperature exceeding 1500 °C. However, the available data indicate that the fuel was not all subjected to high temperature, so some portion of tritium can still remain in fuel matrix. Perhaps, this tritium is washed out by internal waters of SO being accumulated in them. Tritium concentration in the internal waters of SO bottom premises ranges from 1136 Bq/l to 23194 Bq/l (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Concentration of tritium in the groundwater (superficial Quaternary aquifer) within the Chernobyl NPP operating site, as of April 1997, lg T Bq/l

Concentration of tritium in groundwater varies from 2 Bq/l to 5000 Bq/l. Besides, the increase of volumetric activity of tritium was observed in 1998 as compared to 1996-1997 for wells located in the vicinity of SO along the direction of groundwater flow

These data along with another information (distribution of pH values, concentration of sulphates, chlorides, phosphates, nitrates, potassium, organic matter, lead and others) allowed us to make a conclusion about possible income of internal SO waters to geological media.

CONCLUSIONS

There exists two main sources of technogenous contaminants income (including radionuclides) to groundwater in SO area. They are – possible losses of internal SO waters and soils within operating site contaminated during the nuclear accident.. The possibility of water leakage out of destroyed power unit is indicated by appearance in groundwater of certain chemical elements and compounds (or their increased concentration) in the direction of lateral groundwater flow from SO. These chemical substances such as sodium, potassium, sulphates, nitrates, iron, fluorine, phosphates, organic matter, lead were injected into the damaged power unit in the course of fire extinguishing, deactivation and dust-depressing measures. Moreover the possibility of income of the internal waters to geological environment is indicated by existence of large amounts of tritium in groundwater sampled from wells close to SO. Consequently, SO is intensive potential source of groundwater radionuclide contamination.

* by 5.11E-2 is meant 5.11×10^{-2}

** by chloride-hydrocarbonate water is meant the prevalent concentration of hydrocarbonate ion

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are grateful to researchers of Scientific-Technical Center «Shelter», National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine who carried out sampling of soils and water in dangerous conditions of highly radioactive zone of SO. We also express our thanks to the analytical chemists team of Radioecological Center, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine and Research Center for Radiation Medicine, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine who helped us in accomplishing studies described in this paper.

REFERENCES

- Atlas of Chernobyl exclusion zone edited by Shestopalov V.M.. 1996. "Kartografiya", Kyiv,. 26 p.
- Borovoy A.A., Klyuchnikov A.A., Shcherbin V.N., 1996: Problems of safety of the object "Shelter". In: Object "Shelter" – 10 years after. The main results of research studies, Chernobyl 1996, 7-22.
- Krinityn A.P., Simanovskaia I.Ya., Strykhar' O.L., et al. 1998: Research of water interaction with construction and fuel-bearing matters inside the "Shelter" object. Radiochemistry, Vol.40, no. 3, 279-288.
- Onyshchenko I.P., Shestopalov V.M., Panasyuk N.I., 1998: Radio-hydrogeochemiccaal Monitoring of Area Adjacent to the "Shelter" object. In: International Radiological Post-Emergency Response Issues Conference. Meeting Proceedings. September 1998, 233-238.